

[RCRI) was assumed to adequately represent total tiller growth; 2) tillers may recover from infection, and a rate of disease recovery (Recov) was included; 3) severe infection on individual tillers may lead to their death, and a rate of tiller death (Rmort) was included; 4) tiller senescence (Tsen) was also included, and represented as an exponential decay function. This series of equations was linked together and integrated using a 1-d time-step.

Empirical values were derived for the rates of senescence, mortality, and recovery from field experiments at IRRI. An intrinsic rate of primary inoculum decay was derived from published data ($k = -0.11$; Roy [1986]). Data from field experiments (Gou et al 1983) were then used as a basis for model verification, and to estimate the three parameters of the equation for the rate of infection: r_p , r_s , and a . This was achieved

2. Comparison of observed (dots) data and simulated (line) ShB incidence. Observed data were derived from Gou et al (1983).

using disease incidence (i.e., $N_i/(N+Ni)$) as a synthetic variable representing the processes underlying a ShB epidemic, and the DUD interactive technique of the NLIN procedure of the statistical package SAS. Using this technique, parameter estimates were $r_p = 0.04$, $r_s = 0.09$, and $a = 1.77$.

The results of the simulation indicate that this system model has the potential of adequately describing ShB epidemics, and may serve as a basis for further improvement (Figure 2). Experiments are currently under way at IRRI to further assess the performance of the model and to better document r_s in terms of climatic factors and contact frequency among tillers in a rice crop.

Cited references

- Gou FS, Li XQ, Xu CL. 1983. Study on the spatial distribution patterns of the rice sheath blight plant in rice field and its practical applications. *Acta Phytopathol. Sin.* 13:77-34.
- Roy AK. 1986. Survival of sclerotia of *Rhizoctonia solani* F. sp. *sasakii* in relation to moisture regime of soil. *Indian Phytopathol.* 39:259-263. ■

A simulation model of rice sheath blight epidemics (II) Model performance derived from sensitivity analysis

S. Savary, IRRI-ORSTOM Joint Project on Rice Pest Characterization, IRRI; and L. Willocquet, ORSTOM

A preliminary simulation model of rice sheath blight (ShB) epidemics was developed, which incorporates a few important characteristics of the disease: a rate of primary infection (which is proportional to the amount of primary, soilborne inoculum, the amount of healthy tissues [tillers] available for new infection, and an intrinsic rate of primary infection, r_p) and a rate of secondary infection (which is proportional to the amount of infected tissues (tillers) and an intrinsic rate of secondary infection, r_s). The rate of secondary infection also depends on the amount of tissues still available for infection and on an aggregation parameter, a .

This model addresses a few research issues, such as 1) the relative effect of variation of parameter values on the behavior of the model; 2) the contribution

A series of simulation runs using a sheath blight simulation model, with varying values of three parameters: r_p (a), r_s (b), and a (c).

of primary inoculum, relative to that of secondary inoculum, resulting in spread of the disease within the rice crop canopy; and 3) the magnitude of the effect of disease aggregation on disease spread.

The figure shows a series of scenarios where the three parameters were independently varied, using optimized parameter values ($r_p = 0.04$, $r_s = 0.09$, and $a = 1.77$) as references. A series of ShB incidence progress curves were generated by increasing or decreasing r_p and r_s by 25% or 50% of their initial values. Because a cannot, by definition, be smaller than 1, the following values were tested: 1 (random distribution of disease throughout the epidemic), 1.39, 1.77 (optimized value), 2.16, and 2.54.

Variation in r_p (Fig. a) has a small effect on the shape of disease epidemics, a decrease of r_p resulting primarily in a delay of the epidemics with the same speed.

Variation in r_s (Fig. b) has strong effects on both the slopes of the curves and the terminal incidences. As expected, variation in a (Fig. c) affects the shape of curves in a later stage of disease epidemic—the larger the a value, the stronger the disease aggregation. The lower the accessibility of healthy tillers

to diseases, and the slower the epidemic when it enters the polycyclic phase.

This behavior of the model indicates that it is sensitive to variation in r_s . Future development of the model must consider the effect of time-dependent factors on

variation in r_s so as to reflect variation of environment under which ShB epidemics develop. This suggests that the polycyclic nature of ShB must be considered a key characteristic of the disease for its management, and that measures taken in the course

of a cropping season should prove effective. It also indicates a comparatively high sensitivity of the model to variation in the aggregation parameter, and experiments are necessary for its estimation. ■

Use of CERES-Rice model to assess potential yield

G. S. L. H. V. Prasada Rao and N. Subash, Regional Agricultural Research Station (RARS), Pilicode 671353, Kasaragod District, Kerala, India

We conducted a field experiment at RARS, Pilicode ($12^{\circ} 12' N$; $75^{\circ} 10' E$; 2755 mm rainfall, 4.4 h of bright sunshine d^{-1}) to test the CERES-Rice model developed under the IBSNAT Project. Soils were well-drained sandy loam of lateritic origin with pH 5.5. The model was tested for five cropping seasons using different dates of transplanting during 1993 and 1994 kharif and 1992-93, 1993-94, and 1994-95 rabi. Popular varieties Jaya (120-125 d), Jyothi (110-125d), and Triveni (95-105d) were used.

The simulated grain yield through the CERES-Rice model was in good agreement with the observed yield during 1993 kharif while simulated grain yield was higher than that of the observed during 1994 kharif on all transplanting dates (Figs. a and b). Heavy rains during 1994 kharif brought floods. Incidence of gall midge and rice bug was also high at the time, leading to a high percentage of grain chaffing (see table).

The CERES-Rice model during rabi runs for a floodwater management scheme and takes into account bund height as well as floodwater maintained through irrigation at three different early stages of crop growth. The actual rabi crop at the field site was in a totally different condition from that mentioned previously. However, it should be noted that the CERES-Rice model simulated higher grain when run during rabi in all three test varieties on all transplanting dates.

This study reveals that the CERES-Rice model needs validation for rabi while it could very well be used during kharif to assess potential grain yields based on simple daily weather variables. ■

a. Actual and simulated grain yield ($t\ ha^{-1}$) of rice varieties on different dates of transplanting during 1993 kharif.

b. Actual and simulated grain yield ($t\ ha^{-1}$) of rice varieties on different dates of transplanting during 1994 kharif.

Percentage of grain chaffing of three test varieties during 1994 kharif on different dates of transplanting. Kerala, India, 1992-95.

Date of transplanting	Jaya		Jyothi		Triveni	
	Good grains (%)	Chaffing (%)	Good grains (%)	Chaffing (%)	Good grains (%)	Chaffing (%)
8 Jun	68.7	31.3	81.1	18.9	90.3	9.7
15 Jun	82.7	17.3	83.6	16.4	88.7	11.3
22 Jun	75.2	24.8	71.6	28.4	82.8	17.2
29 Jun	67.9	32.1	63.0	37.0	84.0	16.0
6 Jul	58.3	41.7	65.0	35.0	64.2	35.8
Av	70.6	29.4	72.9	27.1	82.0	18.0

Environment

Effect of contour hedgerow on runoff, soil loss, and upland rice production

C. R. Subudhi, P. C. Pradhan, and P. C. Senapati, Dry Land Agricultural Research Project (DLAP), Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Phulbani 7602001, Orissa, India

Most of the hilly areas in Orissa lose a lot of soil during the wet season. Soil loss and runoff, as affected by different contour hedgerows, were quantified and their effects on upland rice production determined.

The study was conducted at DLAP sites in Bhawanipatna in 1993 and in Phulbani in 1994. Soil at both sites is sandy loam with about 2% slope.

Rice (variety 9991 in 1993 and Heera in 1994) was dry-seeded in rows with 20-cm spacing along contours. Hedgerows separated rice terraces. The treatments (9 in 1993 and 7 in 1994) arranged in randomized complete block with three replications were the vegetation used to form the hedgerows (see table).

The hedgerows were planted with 1-yr-old grass seedlings (except for stylo where seeds were sown) 1 mo before the experiment. The distance between two hedgerows was 8 m. Plots were 25 m \times 3 m. Lengthwise, each plot comprised three terraces separated by two hedgerows.

Daily runoff was monitored using a multislit divisor. Runoff collected by one slit is fed into a drum installed at the end of the divisor. A sample of 250 ml was taken from each drum after thorough stirring and